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IMPACT OF MOTIVATION ON JOB PERFORMANCE AND SATISFACTION OF HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN FEDERAL MEDICAL CENTRE JALINGO, TARABA STATE-NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper assessed the impact of motivation on job performance and satisfaction of healthcare workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State-Nigeria. Data were collected from the primary source using a survey research design. A sample of 80 respondents was drawn and used to represent the entire population of the study. The research instrument was validated and tested using Alpha Cronbach with a reliability coefficient of 0.80. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation. The Results showed that good leadership, recognition, good work-life balance, good company culture and royalty from management, good wages, good working conditions, promotion, financial benefits, and job security were identified as the main factors that motivate the job performance of health workers. The result also showed that motivation promotes quality service delivery, motivation raises job satisfaction, fosters persistency in reaching a specific goal, yields better results, motivation promotes effectiveness and efficiency, and encourages workers' self-confidence toward goal attainment. Lack of good leadership, uncertainties, insufficient availability of resources and opportunities, the attitude of workers, fear of success, and fear of failure were found in this study as the main factors militating against health workers' motivation in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State. It is therefore recommended that: The management of Federal Medical Centre Jalingo should pay attention to the improvement of employee empowerment, benefits package; work conditions & recognition in connection with their job performance practices; there is a need for performance standards to be measured by criteria directly related to the job and derived from a thorough job analysis.

KEY WORDS

Motivation, Employee, Effect, Job Performance, Satisfaction.

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Introduction

Motivation is an energizing factor that keeps the workers committed to their duties and helps them do their jobs seriously and joyfully. One of the reasons for the success of employees and thus organizations is the presence of motivational factors at a high degree in those organizations. The concept of motivation is used to explain the distinction between employees which have the same talents, abilities and opportunities to do their jobs in a similar organization and are under the same employment conditions and with the same facilities, but demonstrate different performances. These employees perform their jobs in such a manner that the jobs are required to be done with relatively more efforts, so they can try more to play the role for which they are asked. Thus, improved productivity is driven by positively motivated employees by the organization (Oosthuizen, 2020).

Bolman and Deal (2018) confirmed that when workers are dissatisfied with their work they withdraw and exhibit behaviours such as absenteeism, rebellion and attitude that affects their performance which leads to loss of productivity and effectiveness in the organization but if they are satisfied with their jobs they effectively utilize their skills and the organization benefits. Bearing this in mind one can see that satisfaction at job is important to both the workers and organization. An employee, who is intrinsically motivated, undertakes tasks with satisfaction, for the feeling of accomplishment and self-actualization. On the other hand, an extrinsically motivated employee may perform activity duty in order to obtain a reward such as salary (Din, 2018). Therefore, the aim of the organization such as hospitals should be to build on and enhance extrinsic motivation for its workers to perform the healthcare service effectively, but also at the same time to supply some of intrinsic motivation along the way for organization improvement.

The performance of health care workers depends on ability, tools or equipment and motivation. While motivation is seen as the most important, it is also the most difficult to manage (Reem, 2021). The reason is that if a worker lacks ability or knowledge to perform, a training programme can help to acquire more skills as well as tools can be provided if there is none. However, if motivation is the problem, there will be difficulty in determining what could be done to motivate the employee to work harder and well (Griffin & Moorhead, 2017).

Health workers are part of a country's health system and they are very important in improving health outcomes. Therefore, adequately trained, skilled and motivated health workers in appreciable numbers at facilities where they are needed, is essential in the delivery of quality health care (WHO, 2016). There are certain things that can be done to motivate health workers. For instance, adequate human resource management tools can uphold and strengthen the professional ethics of health workers; acknowledging the career goals including recognition, career development and continuous studies; and also developing the work environment will enable health workers meet personal and organizational goals (Mathawe & Imhoff, 2016).

The Federal Medical Centre, Jalingo cannot exempt itself from health worker motivation. It is assumed that the compelling and competing demands facing the hospital are affecting the best delivery of health care to patients since it is the nation's premier teaching hospital. Shortage of staff cuts across all clinical staff, including nurses, doctors, midwives, biomedical scientists and pharmacists in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo. It is anticipated that the implication of this trend affects provision of quality health care to the clients because there is inadequate human resource, thus increasing workload. It is becoming increasingly difficult as this trend is affecting the motivation and performance of staff. Even though management had instituted some motivational packages, including award to staff members, it is believed that more could be done to cover a greater number of staff as the current coverage is limited. It is known that migration/emigration of health workers from Federal Medical Centre, Jalingo to better and well-endowed clinics and hospitals is becoming common. This migration has created problems of understaffing and demotivation of staff due to excessive workload, poor supervision and lack of continuous education programmes for staff. Thus, this paper is aimed at exploring the influence of motivation on health workers' performance. This would contribute to identifying priority areas of intervention at the level to improve health worker delivery of care to clients and improving the health status of healthcare workers in Taraba State as a whole.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to assess the impact of motivation on job performance and satisfaction of healthcare workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State. The specific objectives sought to:

- i. Identify the factors that motivate job performance of health workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State;
- ii. Evaluate the effects of motivation on job performance and satisfaction of healthcare workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State;
- iii. Ascertain the factors militating against health workers' motivation in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State.

Research Questions

This research work was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What are the factors that motivate job performance of health workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State?
- ii. What are the effects of motivation on job performance and satisfaction of healthcare workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State?
- iii. What are the factors militating against health workers' motivation in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State?

Literature Review

Conceptual Clarifications

The Concept of Motivation

The concept of motivation is used to explain the distinction between employees which have the same talents, abilities and opportunities to do their jobs in a similar organization and are under the same employment conditions and with the same facilities, but demonstrate different performances. These employees perform their jobs in such a manner that the jobs are required to be done with relatively more efforts, so they can try more to play the role for which they are asked (Ramprasad, 2018). Thus, the author affirmed that, improved productivity is driven by positively motivated employees by the organization. In addition, awareness of the motivating factors and factors leading to increased job satisfaction allow the implementation of targeted strategies of continuous improvement in workplace.

Motivation is a critical factor has become increasingly important in the profession of nursing which mainly comprises of emotions and sensitivities; committed health workers are more likely to perform beyond of their duty to meet patients' needs and highly motivated to work to the best of their abilities. These traits are crucial for commitment and ongoing revenue and growth of a hospital. Committed health workers remained in the employment of the hospital longer, resisted competitive job offers, did not actively look for other employment and re hospital to others as a best place to work (Ezzatabadi et al., 2018).

Impacts of Motivation on Performance and the Delivery of Quality Care

There is a significant relationship between motivation and performance. If individuals are highly motivated they will perform better, thus improving the quality of health care delivered. On the other hand, better performance may lead to a sense of achievement resulting in greater motivation (Ali & Howaidee, 2018).

Motivated health workers may do more work, but careful management must be ensured so that they do not spend most of their energy on aspects of work they find stimulating, which may not be of benefit to the organization. When motivated individuals are provided with the requisite skills to do the job, it is also important to improve ability, good selection and training as well as pay attention to motivation (Karan, 2019). In addition, the author added that a motivated and qualified workforce is critical to increase the productivity and quality of health services in order to contribute to achieving health services targets.

Improved performance will mean availability, meaning improved waiting time, adequate staff ratios and attendance of health workers. Competency mean adherence to protocol during diagnosis and communication with patients. Productivity occupancy rate provided per worker or facility and being responsive will lead to client satisfaction, reduction in case fatality rates and reduction in services (WHO, 2016).

The working environment of a health facility will make great strides in improving the effectiveness and quality of the services provided by the health worker. Health workers are responsive to the needs of their clients, but sometimes the services they provide may be timely. The enthusiasm with which the health worker perform serve as a motivation for the health workers to improve their performance and that of the health sector (Reem, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

Frederick Herzberg's two-factor (Motivation Hygiene) Theory

Herzberg (1959), studied people's attitude towards their jobs and asked respondents to describe situations in which they felt happy or unhappy (Dieleman, Toonen, Touré, & Martineau, 2016). While happiness was related to the work itself, unhappiness was related to the conditions that surrounded the job. Based on this, Herzberg (1959) developed a two factor theory that certain group of factors (motivations) lead to job satisfaction whereas another group (hygiene factors) prevent dissatisfaction. The motivating factors are intrinsic and the primary cause of job satisfaction (Dieleman *et al.*, 2016). These include achievement, recognition, responsibility, growth and advancement. The authors further asserted that the motivation factors lead to satisfaction because people desire to grow and to become successful. The hygiene factors are extrinsic to the job. These are the conditions that surround the job and include company policy, job security, supervision, interpersonal relation and salary/pay. Higher salaries make employees happier, but when it is absent it makes people angry and lead to dysfunctional teams (Dieleman *et al.*, 2016). Herzberg (1959) emphasized that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are not the opposite of each other. The opposite of satisfaction is not dissatisfaction, but no satisfaction and the opposite of dissatisfaction not satisfaction, but no dissatisfaction (Chyung, 2020).

Empirical Studies

Alhassan *et al.* (2019) studied the association between health worker motivation and health care quality efforts in Ghana. These researchers identified that most of the health facilities did not document the evidence of processes for continuous quality improvement safety. On the whole staff motivation was seen as low, although workers in the private facilities perceived improved conditions than workers in the public facilities supporting the fact that more comprehensive staff motivation was needed to improve quality strategies.

John (2018) assessed the level of motivation to perform among healthcare workers in Primary Health Care Facilities in Ilemela District of Mwanza city. A survey was carried with 52 healthcare workers that included nurses, doctors and health inspectors. In addition, in- depth interviews were carried out with some nurses and doctors. Data are analyzed using statistics package for social sciences (SPSS) version 16.0. The study revealed that the healthcare workers motivation to join the medical service profession was due to job security and absence of job alternative and salary was not a concern. Overall, level of motivation among workers was low due to low or absence of re-numerations to supplement salary. The study further revealed that the currently used motivational tools were inadequate and undesired.

Lencho (2020) evaluated employee level of motivational and their level of job performance. In order to meet this objective, the researcher has used simple random sampling techniques; in collected from 179 employees out of 287, using Likert scale questionnaires. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (correlation and regression). The result of the descriptive statistics finding indicated that the employee job performance has been under practiced in Fiche General Hospital. The results of inferential statistics have revealed that all motivational factors under study are positively related to employee job performance. According to this finding the employee empowerment practices is more significantly associated and has impacts on employee job performance than all motivational factors under study.

Annie (2016) determined the influence of motivation on health worker performance. Methods: This study applied an exploratory cross sectional design using quantitative methods. The study sample included a total of

324 clinical health personnel from the Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital. Self-administered structured questionnaires were used to collect data from participants. Statistical analysis used was descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used to analyze the socio demographic variables. Univariate, bivariate and multinomial logistic regression tests were employed to analyze relationship between socio demographic and intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors and how these motivational factors influences health workers' performance. Results revealed that majority of the respondents agreed that intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors influence the performance of health workers and consequently improve the quality of health care. Multinomial regression revealed that achievement, recognition and effective supervision improved work performance, however incentive was not significantly associated with performance; improved salary, availability of equipment, availability of adequate human resource and good interpersonal relationship enhanced worker performance.

Mohammad and Tengku (2019) investigated the effect of motivation on job performance of nurses at hospitals in Jordan. Refer to this, a self-administered questionnaire was used and a total of 384 nurses in Jordanian hospital were randomly selected as respondents, in which their perceptions were gathered. The hypothesis was tested by using SEM-AMOS package 22.0 and the findings have shown a direct effect of motivation on Job Performance of Nurses in Jordanian Hospitals, which is positive and significant ($\beta=0.666$, $P=.001$).

Fotis and Maria (2021) investigated the dynamics that may be behind health workers at a public hospital in Northern Greece. Data were collected from 74 employees in the hospital and were analyzed using ANOVA analysis. The results show that key motivators for the employees can be considered the relationships with their colleagues and the level of achievement, while the level of rewards and job characteristics play a secondary role. These results make it clear that, in order for the hospital's management to be able to improve the level of employee performance, it should ensure the establishment of a strong climate among employees, and also acknowledge the efforts made by them.

Methodology

Research Design: Research design for this study was a survey research design. This study made use of a structured questionnaire constructed by the researcher to source data for the conduct of the study.

Study Area: This study is conducted in the Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State. The hospital within the limits of its available resources, has been able to provide high standard of healthcare to its teeming clients; provided with state-of-the-art equipment in the theatres, laboratories, radio-diagnosis, Special Care Baby Unit (SCBU), Obstetrics and Gynecology unit, Family planning unit, Dialysis Unit etc., which are intended to provide patient-friendly and conducive working environment for its staff.

Population of the Study: Population of the study entails the entire geographical area to be covered by the research work. Hence, the population for this research work covered the entire healthcare workers in the Federal Medical Centre Jalingo with the estimated population of over one hundred (100) health workers (FM CJ, 2021).

Sample and Sampling Technique: Sample size is the proportion of the generalized number of population encompassed in the study location for the period under study. Therefore, this study covers eighty (80) respondents which were randomly selected using purposive sampling technique with the aid of Taro Yamane sample size determination technique as shown below.

$$N = n / 1 - N(e)^2$$

Where,

n = sample size

N = population=100

E = level of significance

Therefore;

$$N = 100/1+100(0.05)^2$$

$$N = 100/1.25$$

$$N = 80$$

Study Instrument: The instrument adopted for data collection was the use of a self-structured questionnaire constructed by the researcher in line with the specific research objectives. The questionnaires were administered to the selected respondents in the study area. The study instrument contained an introductory letter from the researcher to the respondents introducing the researcher and the topic for the study.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument: A measuring instrument is considered valid only when it measures truly and accurately what it intends to measure. The instrument constructed by the researcher was validated and the reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Alpha Cronbach's reliability test criteria which revealed the reliability coefficient of 0.80. Hence, this result showed that the instrument is considered reliable, because the closer the result to positive one (1) the more reliable the instrument becomes.

Method of Data Collection

Primary data were collected and used for the purpose of this study. Primary data were collected through the use of structured questionnaires administered to the respondents in the study area. The questionnaire were set in line with specific research objectives of the study which was divided into two parts namely: Sections (A) comprised the demographic data of the respondents and Section (B) comprised questions seeking for the opinions of the respondents with respect to the specific research questions were answered by circling or ticking the option that best expressed the feeling of the respondents to the specific research questions.

Method of Data Analysis: Data collected through questionnaires on socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents were statistically presented and analyzed using frequency tables and simple percentage, but data collected in responses to the specific research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation with help of SPSS version 23.

Results

In this paper, descriptive statistics were used to sort, code, present and analyzed data collected for the conduct of the study. Demographic data were presented in tabular form while responses from the questionnaire were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Eighty (80) questionnaires were distributed, but only sixty eight (68) were duly filled and returned.

Table 1: Classification of Respondents according to their Age

Years	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18 – 30	20	30.0
31 – 40	31	45.0
41 – 50	14	20.0
51 & above	3	5.00
Total	68	100.0

Table 2: Classification of Respondents according to their Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
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Female	44	65.2
Male	24	34.8
Total	68	100.0

Table 3: Classification of Respondents according to their Qualification

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No formal education	2	1.7
Primary	6	8.3
Secondary	20	29
Tertiary	40	61
Total	98	100.0

Table 4: Classification of Respondents according to their Marital Status

Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	23	34.3
Married	41	60.7
Widow	3	4.00
Divorced	2	1.00
Total	68	100.0

Table 5: Classification of Respondents according to their Working Experience

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
0 – 3	6	8.70
4 – 6	12	18.0
7 – 10	29	42.3
11 Years & above	21	31.0
Total	68	100.0

Table 6: Classification of Respondents according to their Profession

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Nurse/ Midwife	23.8	35
Physician and health officer	14.0	20
Laboratory technicians and technologist	8	12
Doctor/Pharmacist	20	30
Others	2	3
Total	68	100.0

Table 7: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Factors that Motivate Workers

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std	Decision
1	Good leadership	68	3.8895	.42951	Accepted
2	Recognition and good work life balance	68	3.8784	.64643	Accepted

3	Rewards and appreciation	68	3.7985	.56248	Accepted
4	Good company culture and royalty from management	68	3.8611	.52716	Accepted
5	Professional development opportunities	68	3.7553	.43733	Accepted
6	Job advancement opportunities	68	3.6598	.33308	Accepted
7	Financial benefits and job security	68	3.8043	.63087	Accepted
8	Good working conditions	68	3.8376	.54478	Accepted
9	Good wages	68	3.8575	.24359	Accepted
10	Promotion	68	3.8325	.04357	Accepted

Table 8: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Effects of Motivation on Job Performance and Satisfaction

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std	Decision
1	Motivation increases workers' energy level for more productivity	68	3.6942	.42951	Accepted
2	Fosters persistency in reaching a specific goal	68	3.8473	.64643	Accepted
3	Motivation improves workers' learning ability	68	3.6324	.56248	Accepted
4	It encourages workers self-confidence towards goals attainment	68	3.7854	.52716	Accepted
5	Motivation raises job satisfaction	68	3.8758	.43733	Accepted
6	It yields better results	68	3.8375	.33308	Accepted
7	Motivation promotes effectiveness and efficiency	68	3.8294	.63087	Accepted
8	Raises high profitability	68	3.7943	.54478	Accepted
9	Motivation promotes quality service delivery	68	3.8842	.24359	Accepted
10	It encourages team work which fosters sectoral growth and development	68	3.6587	.60284	Accepted

Table 9: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Factors Militating against Health Workers' Motivation

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std	Decision
1	Fear of failure	68	3.7695	.42951	Accepted
2	Fear of success	68	3.7806	.64643	Accepted
3	Lack of clarity	68	3.6321	.56248	Accepted
4	Low self-confidence	68	3.5986	.52716	Accepted
5	Poor communication skills	68	3.4398	.43733	Accepted
6	Insufficient availability of resources and opportunities	68	3.8528	.33308	Accepted
7	Uncertainties	68	3.8679	.63087	Accepted
8	Attitude of workers	68	3.8291	.54478	Accepted
9	Inadequate technological advancement	68	3.2912	.24359	Accepted
10	Lack of good leadership	68	3.8878	.60284	Accepted

Discussion

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents based on age, it shows that 30% are between the ages of 18 – 30 years, 45% are between the ages of 31 – 40 years, 20% are between the ages of 41 – 50 years and 5.0% are between the ages of 51 years and above respectively. It therefore shows that majority of the respondents are between the ages of 31 – 40 years old.

Table 2 above reveals that 65.2% of the entire respondents are female while 34.8% are male. Hence, indicates that most of the respondents are female who responded to the research instrument.

Table 3 shows that 1.7% of the respondents have no formal education; 8.3% have primary school certificate (FSLC); 29% of the same respondents have Secondary school certificate (SSCE) and 61% of the respondents have Tertiary educational qualification. Hence, most of the respondents have tertiary education that constitutes the majority of the respondents.

Table 4 above reveals that 34.3% of the entire respondents are single; 60.7% are married; 4% are widows/widowers and 1% is divorced. Thus, majority of the respondents are married.

Table 5 showed that 8.70% of the respondents have the working experience of 0 – 3 years; 18% have the working experience of 4 – 6 years; 42.3% have the working experience of 7 – 10 years and 31% of the entire respondents have the working experience of 11 years and more respectively. By implication, majority of the respondents have good working experience.

Table 6 shows that 35% of the entire respondents are Nurses and Midwives; 20% are Physician and health officer; 12% are Laboratory technicians and technologist; 30% are doctors and pharmacists and 3% of them are either cleaners or clerical assistants respectively.

Table 7 revealed that, good leadership, recognition and good work life balance, good company culture and royalty from management, good wages, good working conditions, promotion and financial benefits and job security were identified as the main factors that motivate job performance of health workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State. These were supported with the mean scores of 3.8895, 3.8784, 3.8611, 3.8575, 3.8376, 3.8325 and 3.8043. Other factors include: rewards and appreciation, professional development opportunities and job advancement opportunities respectively.

Table 8 shows that, motivation promotes quality service delivery, motivation raises job satisfaction, fosters persistency in reaching a specific goal, it yields better results, motivation promotes effectiveness and efficiency and it encourages workers self-confidence towards goals attainment. These were identified as the main effects of motivation on job performance and satisfaction of healthcare workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State. These were supported with the mean scores of 3.8842, 3.8758, 3.8473, 3.8375, 3.8294 and 3.7854 respectively. Other effects of motivation include: Raises high profitability, it encourages workers self-confidence towards goals attainment, it encourages team work which fosters sectoral growth and development, motivation improves workers' learning ability and motivation increases workers' energy level for more productivity.

Table 9 shows that, lack of good leadership, uncertainties, insufficient availability of resources and opportunities, attitude of workers, fear of success and fear of failure were found in this study as the main factors militating against health workers' motivation in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State. These were supported with the mean scores of 3.8878, 3.8679, 3.8528, 3.8291, 3.7806 and 3.7695. Other factors identified in this study include: lack of clarity, low self-confidence, poor communication skills and inadequate technological advancement respectively.

Conclusion

This study assessed the impact of motivation on job performance and satisfaction of healthcare workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State. The findings of this study showed that, good leadership, recognition and good work life balance, good company culture and royalty from management, good wages, good working conditions, promotion and financial benefits and job security were identified as the main factors that motivate job performance of health workers in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State.

Motivation promotes quality service delivery, motivation raises job satisfaction, fosters persistency in reaching a specific goal, it yields better results, motivation promotes effectiveness and efficiency and it encourages workers self-confidence towards goals attainment.

Lack of good leadership, uncertainties, insufficient availability of resources and opportunities, attitude of workers, fear of success and fear of failure were found in this study as the main factors militating against health workers' motivation in Federal Medical Centre Jalingo, Taraba State.

Recommendations

Upon analysis of the data and the resulting evidence obtained from the research, the following recommendations were provided:

- i. The management of Federal Medical Centre Jalingo should pay attention for improvement of employee empowerment, benefits package; work condition & recognition in connection with their job performance practices. It advantageous, if the management of FMC, Jalingo wisely work towards developing a mechanism to motivate their needy employee on these identified gaps.
- ii. It is also valuable, if the management intervention is undertaken to visit their employee's level of their employee job performance and support them on the identified motivational factors. In order to enhance the employee motivation and their job performance at FMC, Jalingo, the management of that organization is suggested to assess their employee's needs periodically to take proper action for better organizational functioning.
- iii. There is the need for employees to be involved at all stages of designing motivational factors that directly influence performance to ensure buy in from all.
- iv. There is the need for employees as well as managers to be educated thoroughly on the impact of motivational factors on performance. This will ensure that subjectivity and office politicking do not distort the reviews. Managers should have the ability to listen, coach, counsel and develop rather than focus on judgment alone.
- v. There is the need for a feedback mechanism to be created to enable employees to also assess their motivational levels and performance themselves.
- vi. There is the need for performance standards to be measured by criteria directly related to the job and derived from a thorough job analysis.

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